

**SYNTHESIS OF 9-KETO-2-METHYL-1:2-CYCLOPENTANO-
1:2:3:4:4a:4b:5:6:7:8:8a:9:10:10a-TETRADECAHYDRO-
PHENANTHRENE**

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The condensation of 1-acetyl- $\Delta^{1:3}$ -cyclohexene with 8-methyl-0:3:4-bicyclononane-4-one (I) in presence of potassium *tert.*-butoxide furnished 9-keto-2-methyl-1:2-cyclopentano-1:2:3:4:4a:4b:5:6:7:8:8a:9-dodecacydrophenanthrene (III) which was reduced by lithium in liquid ammonia to 9-keto-2-methyl-1:2-cyclopentano-1:2:3:4:4a:4b:5:6:7:8:8a:9:10:10a-tetradecacydrophenanthrene. This compound was oxidised to the lactone (VI) which on hydrolysis yielded the hydroxy-acid (VII). The hydroxy-acid was transformed back to the lactone (I).

Bagchi and Banerjee (this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 397) condensed 8-methyl-0:3:4-bicyclononane-4-one (I) with 1-methyl-2-acetyl- $\Delta^{1:3}$ -cyclohexene according to Huber's condition (*Ber.*, 1938, 71, 725) and the structure (II) was assigned to the condensation product on the basis of latter's report. In view of the more recent publications on similar condensations (Turner and Voitle, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4166; Johnson *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1950, 72, 3726; Braude and Wheeler, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 329) the product obtained by Bagchi and Banerjee should be regarded as a mixture.

In view of recent recognition of high physiological activity of 19-nor-steroid (Birch and Mukherjee, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2531; Wilds and Nelson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5366; Djerassi *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 4440; 1951, 73, 3540; 1956, 78, 2479; Sandoval *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 4117) the condensation of (I) (Banerjee and Shafer, *ibid.*, 1950, 72, 1931) with 1-acetyl- $\Delta^{1:3}$ -cyclohexene under the condition of Johnson *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) has been studied. To get a clue about the structure of the condensation product, obtained as an oil in 40-50% yield, it was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride and then dehydrogenated, but unfortunately no aromatic hydrocarbon could be isolated. The aforementioned oil on chromatography furnished a crystalline $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone in 27% yield.

To distinguish between the structures (III) and (IV) for the crystalline ketone, it was converted into 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone; the ultraviolet absorption of D.N.P. of (III) may be expected near $390\text{ m}\mu$ and that of (IV), near $404\text{ m}\mu$, as has been shown by Djerassi and Ryan (*ibid.*, 1949, 71, 1000) with Δ^4 -unsaturated-3-keto-steroid and $\Delta^{1,4}$ -unsaturated-3-keto-steroid. The actual absorption at $377\text{ m}\mu$ in ethanol or $384\text{ m}\mu$ in chloroform indicated that the parent ketone might be represented by the structure (III). This conclusion has been proved by the following degradative studies:

The unsaturated ketone was reduced by lithium in liquid ammonia, and since the product, thus obtained, did not show any ultraviolet absorption, it was oxidised following the method of Fieser (*ibid.*, 1953, 75, 4386). This saturated ketone, obtained directly as a crystalline material or through D₂N.P., was treated with perbenzoic acid to furnish the lactone (VI) which was hydrolysed with alkali to the hydroxy-acid (VII) in 85% yield. The structure of the latter was established from its neutral equivalent data and its transformation with dilute sulphuric acid back to the original lactone (cf. Rothman *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1954, 70, 527). The structure (VII) for the hydroxy-acid is preferred because in per-acid oxidation of ketone to lactone the extra oxygen atom usually attaches itself to the more substituted carbon atom (Doering and Speers, *ibid.*,

1950, 72, 5515). The hydroxy-acid was oxidised according to the method of Fieser (*loc. cit.*) and the crude reaction product furnished a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, indicating the formation of the keto-acid (VIII).

Since the starting 8-methyl-0:3:4-bicyclononane-4-one (I) has been proved to be a *cis* compound (Banerjee and Shafer, *loc. cit.*) the ring fusion of C and D of the compound (V) is *cis*. The ring fusion of A and B is most probably *trans* because of C₇-carbonyl group. From analogy with the method of preparation of Rapson-Robinson's ketone (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1285) it may be expected that the backbone of perhydrophenanthrene skeleton (C_{4a}-C_{14b}) is *anti*. The reduction of the C₈-C₉ double bond in steroid with dissolved metal usually produces the more stable configuration; consequently ring fusion of B and C seems to be *trans*. The probable stereochemical configuration of the saturated ketone is represented by (V).

*E X P E R I M E N T A L

9-Keto-2-methyl-1:2-cyclopentano-1:2:3:4:4a:4b:5:6:7:8:8a:9-dodecahydrophenanthrene (III).—To a solution of potassium metal (1.1 g.) in *tert.*-butanol (30 c.c.) was added dropwise with constant shaking under nitrogen atmosphere a solution of 1-acetyl- $\Delta^{1:2}$ -cyclohexene, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 232 m μ (log ϵ 3.96) and the compound (I, 3.9 g.) was prepared according to the procedure of Banerjee and Shafer (*loc. cit.*) in dry thiophene-free benzene (40 c.c.). During the addition the reaction mixture warmed up slightly and the resulting orange-red solution was allowed to stand for 16 hours at room temperature. It was refluxed for 5 hours and then acidified with cold dilute acetic acid. The aqueous layer was separated and most of *tert.*-butanol and benzene were removed under reduced pressure. The residue, thus obtained, was diluted with water and extracted 4 times with ether. The extract was washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water. The solvent was dried and the residue fractionated: (i) b.p. 60-70°/0.8 mm (1.6 g.); (ii) b.p. 160-80°/1 mm (2.7 g.), an almost colorless oil, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 242 m μ (log ϵ 3.94). A portion of the fraction (ii) was redistilled, b.p. 150-55°/0.2 mm. (Found: C, 83.92; H, 9.68. C₁₈H₂₆O requires C, 83.72; H, 10.08%).

The above condensation product (0.85 g.), dissolved in dry ether (40 c.c.), was reduced with powdered LiAlH₄ (0.15 g.) by refluxing for 1 hour. The cooled reaction mixture was decomposed by careful addition of ice-water, followed by an ice-cold H₂SO₄ solution (10%). The acidified solution was thoroughly extracted with ether and the extract was washed with water. The residue, obtained after removal of the solvent, was dried and transferred to a fractionating Claisen flask with dry benzene (30 c.c.). *p*-Toluenesulphonic acid (25-30 mg.) was added to the benzene solution and the reaction mixture was slowly distilled when the distillate (15 c.c.) was collected during one hour. The reaction mixture was cooled and washed with cold dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water. The solvent was removed and the residue was evaporatively distilled to yield a slightly coloured material, b.p. 90-95°/0.15 mm, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 245 m μ (log ϵ 3.95). (Found: C, 89.67; H, 10.38. C₁₈H₂₆ requires C, 89.25; H, 10.74%).

*All melting points are uncorrected. The ultraviolet absorption spectrum was examined by the Unicam spectrophotometer, S.P. 500.

The oily product from the above experiment was dehydrogenated by heating for 3 hours with 30% palladium on charcoal catalyst (0.1 g.) at 250°-320° in Heymann's dehydrogenation apparatus. The reaction product was extracted with ether. After removal of the solvent the residue did not furnish any picrate.

A solution of the aforementioned condensation product (2.7 g.) in dry petroleum ether (b.p. 60°-80°) was adsorbed on a column of activated alumina (Merck & Co., 90 g.) and the chromatogram was first eluted with petroleum ether. Twelve fractions (150 c.c. each) were collected. To each of the fractions a little methanol was added. After a week beautiful crystals with some adhering oil were noticed in each fraction (II to XII). The crystals were combined together and recrystallised once from methanol, yielding (i) solid (0.6 g.), m.p. 85-90° and (ii) an oil (0.3 g.). Fractions obtained when benzene and ether were used as the eluting solvent were combined together (0.7 g.), $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc.}}$ 240 $\mu\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.48) and 249 $\mu\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.5). The oil (1 g.) from the mother-liquor of the above crystallisation and fraction (I) was rechromatographed over alumina (60 g.) using petroleum ether (60°-80°) as the eluting solvent. Twenty fractions (60 c.c. each) were collected. From fractions (X to XX), the crystalline material (0.12 g.), m. 85-90°, was obtained. The oil (0.72 g.) obtained from fractions (I to XX) was evaporatively distilled at 130-40°/0.4 mm, $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc.}}$ 249 $\mu\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.3).

A part of the above crystalline material (70 mg.) was recrystallised three times from dilute methanol to furnish white prisms (20 mg.), m.p. 95.5-96°, $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc.}}$ 243 $\mu\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.13). (Found: C, 83.24; H, 10.73. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}$ requires C, 83.72; H, 10.08%).

The above crystalline unsaturated ketone (53.5 mg.) and 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (40 mg.) were dissolved in absolute ethanol (10 c.c.) by heating and then treated with 2 drops of HCl (conc.). The resulting solution was heated on the steam-bath for 2 minutes and allowed to stand at room temperature when a crystalline material (59 mg.), m.p. 170-71°, separated out. This was recrystallised four times from absolute ethanol to furnish stout orange-red needles, m.p. 175-77°, $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{chl.}}$ 266 $\mu\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.18) and 384 $\mu\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.4); $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc.}}$ 258 $\mu\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.2) and 377 $\mu\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.4). (Found: N, 13.10. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires N, 12.78%).

9-Keto-2-methyl-1:2-cyclopentano-1:2:3:4:4a:4b:5:6:7:8:8a:9:10:10a-tetra-decahydrophenanthrene (V).—To a stirred solution of dry ether (45 c.c.) in anhydrous liquid ammonia (400 c.c.) was added in small pieces lithium metal (300 mg.), followed by the dropwise addition of a solution of the crude unsaturated ketone (III, 300 mg.) in ether (30 c.c.). The stirring was further continued for 20 minutes and then solid ammonium chloride was added in small portions just to discharge the blue colour of the reaction mixture and then left overnight. The residue after addition of cold water was extracted 3-4 times with ether. The ether extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of the solvent the residue was dried under reduced pressure. To a solution of the crude reduction product (300 mg.) in dry benzene (2 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (2 c.c.) was added a solution of sodium dichromate dihydrate (0.2 g.) in glacial acetic acid (2 c.c.). The reaction was allowed to proceed at room temperature for 12 hours. Cold water (50 c.c.) was added to the reaction mixture and after separation of the benzene layer,

the aqueous layer was extracted 4 times with ether. The combined ether-benzene extract was washed twice with cold water, then three times with cold saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with cold water. The solvent mixture was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and on removal of the volatile solvents, the residue was evaporatively distilled at 110-15°/0.2 mm. The sublimate solidified to silky needles with adhering oil (230 mg.), m.p. 62-65°. This was recrystallised 3 times from methanol to furnish white needles (60 mg.), m.p. 73-74°. The mother-liquors were combined together and treated with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine with a few drops of HCl (conc.). The crude D.N.P., m.p. 197-201°, was purified by chromatography on alumina (10 g.) with benzene as the solvent to furnish a material, melting at 213-14° (200 mg.) which was crystallised three times from ethyl acetate to afford orange crystals, m.p. 215-16°; $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 366 m μ (log ϵ 4.15). (Found: N, 12.60. C₂₄H₃₂O₄N₄ requires N, 12.72%).

A solution of the above D.N.P. (200 mg.) in chloroform (11 c.c.), pyruvic acid (11.6 c.c.) of neutral equivalent 90-92 (gift from G.D.A. Chemical Ltd., Calcutta) and approximately 4*N* anhydrous hydrobromic acid in acetic acid (1.3 c.c.) was stirred at 50-60° for 3 hours. The completion of the reaction was indicated by appreciable lightening of the colour of the solution. This was cooled, diluted with water and the chloroform layer was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water. The solvent was dried and evaporated. The residue was chromatographed over alumina (11 g.) and the substance, eluted with petroleum ether, was evaporatively distilled at 105-10°/0.2 mm to yield white crystalline needles (85 mg.), m.p. 69-70° which was crystallised from methanol, m.p., 73-74° and then sublimed at 105-10°/0.2 mm. (Found: C, 83.13; H, 10.96. C₁₈H₂₂O requires C, 83.05; H, 10.83%). The conversion of pure unsaturated ketone (III) to the saturated ketone (V) by the above procedure furnished a better yield (85%).

Lactone of 8-Methyl-5-(2'-hydroxycyclohexyl)-hydrindane-4-acetic Acid (VI).—

(a). To the saturated ketone (100 mg.) in a test tube covered with black paper was added a solution of perbenzoic acid in chloroform (2 c.c., 5.5%), acetic anhydride (0.025 c.c.), acetic acid (0.3 c.c.) and acetone (5 c.c.) and the mixture left for 8 days in a dark place. A blank experiment was also performed simultaneously. After titration, which indicated the utilisation of one mole of perbenzoic acid, the reaction mixture was extracted 3 times with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with sodium thiosulphate, cold 2% NaOH solution and finally with water. After drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the ether was removed and the residue was evaporatively distilled at 110-20°/0.2 mm to yield a solid with adhering gum which was once crystallised from *n*-hexane to furnish white silky needles of the lactone (21 mg.), m.p. 145-46°.

(b). To the saturated ketone (200 mg.) was added a solution of perbenzoic acid in chloroform (4 c.c., 5.5%). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 20 hours in the refrigerator and then 12 hours at room temperature. It was worked up as above and the crude product was evaporatively distilled at 110-20°/0.2 mm to yield a white crystalline solid, m.p. 120-26° which was crystallised several times from *n*-hexane to furnish white silky needles (110 mg.), m.p. 147-48°. (Found: C, 78.42;

H, 10.40. $C_{18}H_{28}O_2$ requires C, 78.26; H, 10.14%). It may be mentioned that the lactone was obtained in 52% yield even when the reaction mixture was allowed to stand only for 24 hours in the refrigerator.

8-Methyl-5-(2'-hydroxycyclohexyl)-hydrindane-4-acetic Acid (VI).—To a solution of the lactone (110 mg.) in distilled methanol (1 c.c.) was added methanolic KOH solution (1 c.c., 10%). The mixture was refluxed for 4 hours on the water-bath. Most of the methanol was removed and water (5 c.c.) was added when a clear solution was obtained. The solution was extracted 3 times with ether. The aqueous solution was acidified with 1% H_2SO_4 solution when a white crystalline solid was precipitated. It was extracted with ether, the extract washed several times with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of the ether the white crystalline residue (100 mg.) was crystallised twice from a mixture of ethyl acetate and petroleum ether to furnish a material of m.p. $148-49^\circ$ which was recrystallised three times from dilute methanol to afford pure hydroxy-acid (44 mg.), m.p. $169-70^\circ$. (Found: C, 73.65; H, 10.43; N.E., 291. $C_{18}H_{30}O_3$ requires C, 73.46; H, 10.20%; N.E., 294). Equal parts of the hydroxy-acid, m.p. $169-170^\circ$, and the lactone, m.p. $147-48^\circ$, were mixed together and the mixture melted at $124-25^\circ$. It may be mentioned that pure hydroxy-acid can be sublimed at $140-50^\circ/0.2$ mm without lactonisation.

The lactonisation of the above hydroxy-acid was performed as follows: Pure hydroxy-acid (16 mg.) was heated with sulphuric acid (10%) for 2 hours on a water-bath. The solid was filtered, dried and sublimed at $115-20^\circ/0.4$ mm. The sublimate (8 mg.), m.p. $145-46^\circ$, was crystallised from *n*-hexane, m.p. $147-48^\circ$. The mixed m.p. of this solid with the pure lactone, $147-48^\circ$, remained undepressed.

Dinitrophenylhydrazone of 8-Methyl-5-(cyclohex-2'-one)-hydrindane-4-acetic Acid.—To a solution of the hydroxy-acid (100 mg.) in dry benzene (1 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (1 c.c.) was added a solution of sodium dichromate dihydrate (0.1 g.) in glacial acetic acid (1 c.c.). The reaction was allowed to proceed in the refrigerator for 12 hours and then worked up as before except the treatment with base. The oily residue after evaporation of the solvent was heated to boiling with methanol (10 c.c.), 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (80 mg.) and a drop of HCl (conc.). The concentrated solution was left at room temperature for 40 hours when a yellow 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone separated out. This was crystallised 3 times from alcohol to furnish yellow silky needles (45 mg.), m.p. $198-99^\circ$, $\lambda_{max}^{alc.}$ 365 m μ (log ϵ 4.35). (Found: N, 11.85, 11.99. $C_{24}H_{32}O_6N_4$ requires N, 11.86%).